

**TREATMENT OF VENOUS TROPHIC ULCERS OF THE
LOWER EXTREMITIES USING THE EVO LASER****Mahmudov G.A.**

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INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE ON
BUSINESS &
MANAGEMENT**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 13th April 2026Accepted: 15th April 2026Online: 17th April 2026**KEYWORDS**

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ABSTRACT

Trophic ulcers developing as a result of chronic venous insufficiency (CVI) of the lower extremities are a significant problem in modern phlebology and surgical practice. This pathology is primarily associated with venous valve insufficiency, venous hypertension, and microcirculation disorders, leading to chronic hypoxia and trophic changes in tissues. As a result, ulcers that do not heal for a long time form on the skin and subcutaneous tissues.

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In addition to traditional conservative and surgical treatment methods, the use of laser technologies has become increasingly popular in recent years. In particular, the Evo laser technology is recognized as a highly effective minimally invasive method for treating venous pathologies. The Evo laser operates on the principle of endovenous laser coagulation (EVLC) and eliminates venous reflux through thermal obliteration of pathologically altered veins.

During laser therapy, the laser beam is directed intravenously through a special fibrous light guide. Laser energy acts on the vein wall, causing its collapse and subsequent fibrosis. As a result, pathological blood flow stops, healthy venous hemodynamics is restored, and favorable conditions are created for the healing of trophic ulcers.

Clinical observations show that after treatment with Evo laser, the epithelialization of trophic ulcers accelerates, inflammation signs decrease, and patients' quality of life improves significantly. The advantages of the method include low invasiveness, a short rehabilitation period, rare complications, and the ability to be performed in outpatient settings.

In conclusion, it can be said that treating trophic ulcers of the lower extremities caused by venous insufficiency using Evo laser is an effective, safe, and modern method that is an important component of the comprehensive treatment strategy.

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